

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.)
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out number below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests)
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common—not trade—names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.)

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Performance of U.S. rice varieties in Afghanistan

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Thirty-seven U.S. rice varieties were tested in observational nurseries at agricultural research stations at Baghlan in the Northern Zone (temperate climate) and at Jalalabad in the Eastern Zone (subtropical climate) in 1966. Thirteen varieties at Baghlan and 24 varieties at Jalalabad grew normally.

In replicated variety trials in 1966-80 under high fertility (120-80-60 kg NPK/ha), 11 varieties appeared promising at both sites. Local fine-grained varieties Barah at Baghlan and Pashadi at Jalalabad, and coarse-grained variety

Luk at both sites were included as checks.

Yields of both fine-grained and coarse-grained U.S. varieties were higher at Baghlan than at Jalalabad (Table 1). At Baghlan, average yields of fine-grained varieties varied from 6.2 t/ha for Starbonnet to 7.8 t/ha for CI 9453 B₆T₅₀ × CI 9187, 9.69-49.11% more than local variety Barah.

Yields of coarse-grained varieties ranged from 6.5 t/ha for Belle Patna to 8.1 t/ha for Arkrose, 50-128% more than the local variety.

At Jalalabad, fine-grained variety yields ranged from 3.1 t/ha for CI 9153 B₆T₅₀ × CI 9810 to 5 t/ha for Starbonnet, 15-44% more than the local variety.

Table 1. Yields of U.S. rices in varietal trials at the agricultural research stations at Baghlan and Jalalabad, Afghanistan, 1966-80.

Variety	Trials (no.)	Average yield (t/ha)		Increase over local variety	
		U.S. variety	Local variety	t/ha	%
<i>Baghlan</i>					
<i>Fine-grained varieties</i>					
CI 9453B ₆ T ₅₀ × CI 9187	10	7.8	5.2	2.6	49
Della	10	7.6	5.6	2.0	36
Kolo Australia	10	7.4	5.0	2.4	49
R7689x (7P × RSBR)	2	7.1	6.4	0.6	10
Saturn	20	6.7	5.4	1.3	23
CI 9453B ₆ T ₅₀ × CI 9810	2	6.6	5.6	0.9	16
Starbonnet	2	6.2	5.6	0.6	11
<i>Coarse-grained varieties</i>					
Arkrose	14	8.1	3.5	4.6	128
Northrose 9407	3	7.6	4.6	3.0	65
Calrose	3	6.6	4.0	2.5	63
Belle Patna	4	6.5	4.4	2.2	50
<i>Jalalabad</i>					
<i>Fine-grained varieties</i>					
CI 9453B ₆ T ₅₀ × CI 9187	5	5.0	3.6	1.3	37
Della	6	3.6	3.2	0.5	15
Kolo Australia	5	4.5	3.3	1.1	33
R7689x (7P × RSBR)	3	4.9	3.5	1.4	39
Saturn	7	3.4	2.4	0.8	33
CI 9453B ₆ T ₅₀ × CI 9810	2	3.1	2.5	0.6	24
Starbonnet	2	5.0	3.4	1.5	44
<i>Coarse-grained varieties</i>					
Arkrose	8	4.4	2.9	1.4	50
Northrose 9407	3	5.9	3.5	2.4	68
Calrose	5	4.3	3.2	1.1	33
Belle Patna	4	3.4	1.5	1.9	122

Table 2. Quality characters of 2 promising U.S. varieties and the quality rice varieties of Afghanistan.

Variety	Origin	Grain appearance			Alkali spread	Gelatinization temperature	Gel consistency (mm)	Amylose (%)	Aroma
		Length	Shape	Chalkiness					
Saturn	USA	Long	Slender	None	4.5	Intermediate	55	21.5	Slight
Della	USA	Extra long	Slender	Small	7.0	Low	100	18.8	Slight
Barah	Afghanistan	Extra long	Slender	Small	6.4	Low	32	22.7	Moderate
Pashadi	Afghanistan	Long	Slender	Large	5.5	Intermediate	60	20.4	Moderate

Coarse-grained variety yields ranged from 3.4 t/ha for Belle Patna to 5.9 t/ha for Northrose 9407, 33-122% more than the local variety.

In evaluation of the fine-grained varieties at IRRI, the quality characters of Saturn and Della compare well with

those of local varieties (Table 2). U.S. variety Saturn was better than the best quality variety of Afghanistan and has become very popular with farmers in the Northern Zone. In the Eastern Zone, it could not compete with the Indian quality rice variety CR44-11 already being

grown.

Local coarse-grained variety Luk is being replaced with Arkrose and Northrose in the Northern and Eastern Zones, where they have yield potentials up to 8.1 t/ha and 6.0 t/ha. ■

Scanning electron microscope studies of the structure and the initial germination stages of rice seed

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In China, experienced farmers sow pre-germinated seed at the white exposed or Lou Bai stage. The scanning electron microscope was used to determine the structural features of seeds at Lou Bai and to study early stages of rice seed germination.

Before germination starts the mature embryo of rice consists of a number of embryonic leaves enclosing an apical meristem and a radicle. The embryonic leaves are enclosed by a cylinder-like covering, the coleoptile. Toward the dorsal side of the caryopsis, between the embryo and the endosperm, is the scutellum. Opposite the scutellum, on the ventral side of the caryopsis, are several interconnecting structures — two scales, the epiblast and the coleorhiza (Fig. 1).

These ventrally located structures are masked by the seed coat and the pericarp of the caryopsis. The two ventral scales originating from the scutellum are free from each other on the ventral side but overlap slightly as they curve inward toward the scutellum.

The two ventral scales and the epiblast enclose only the top half of the embryo, the coleoptile. The bottom half

1. Ventral view of a rice seed embryo after removal of the seed coat and the pericarp.

2. Ventral view of a rice seed embryo at Lou Bai or white exposed stage, about 60 hours after germination. C = coleorhiza, CO = coleoptile, E = epiblast, L = lemma, R = radicle, VS = ventral scales, s = scutellum. Seeds were germinated on wet filter paper in a lighted room at ambient temperature before critical point drying. Specimens were observed in a Cambridge Stereoscan microscope operating at 20 KV. The rice variety was Gui Chao.